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Importance of Equilibrium for all Types of Loadings in Human Body

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ABSTRACT

In general, in practical stressful life, employees suffer a lot of strain; thus, the impact on human health will arise. Thus, in such cases, one needs to come back to the original condition called equilibrium. It is a condition where all directions of forces, all directions of pressures, and all directions of loading will be imposed. In such cases the equilibrium is applied over the human body. This paper discusses how the force can be converted into useful power for a human body. In this case force is directly converted into power as an expansion process. Also how the loadings are made on the human body. The biologically and physically different states of condition of matter are imposing on the human body. As in the zenith, the upper sky species are on the head of the human body; then, with the speed, only the force can be converted into power as an expansion process. Thus, utilizing loading to power as useful to the human body is achieved.

Keywords: *Zenith, nadir, upper sky, lower sky, load, force, physiology, power, space technology*

INTRODUCTION

The generally human working in any environment suffering tension may be in one part of the brain, with other human body parts affected, and then the loading and unloading condition, which is frequently relieved. Here the contraction and expansion are the exact opposite words helpful to release the useful power generating to the human body. The condition of equilibrium is achieved at the space element region only. There is no such kind of enemy for space. The anger and fear come to a person whose stress and strain are severe conditions. These are negative threats, and upon expansion of power, these can be nullified, and hence the force is directly converted into power. In this process, while a person is suffering contraction or pressure or loading on the human body, the lower sky species is acting on the type of loads on the human body. Thus, a person can't feel well in these conditions. Usually lower, as adho direction as hell species are made to contact the human body, then with a speed or method of removing, as in the case of space technology, then only this load can be converted into power as expansion. This is the main output of gaining positive energy for the human body. Psycho patients also suffer this type of loading; after the load reversal process with speed up in space technology, then useful power is obtained. The pressure as a force is divided by the area, then the load is simply the weight as N/m^2 . If putting on sense-level matter of different types, then as lower sky weight, then with the aid of speed in space level as an element, then power is generated, which is required for human beings as in the case of energy creation. [1-27]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In short, the load can be converted into power with light speed in the space element as space technology.

Understanding load as bio-based, which is the negative energy, and hence to be converted into expansion as power. Through space technology, space is an element, and thus it is equivalent to the speed of light. Then sense-level loading is also made into a free body diagram, thus attaining equilibrium, which is the original condition of state and can be made useful as positive energy. After attaining this equilibrium, the energy is released in the form of joy, peace, love, and enlightenment from all angles and all aspects of life.

Conclusion

- The equilibrium is applied over the human body. This paper discusses how the force can be converted into useful power for a human body.
- In this case force is directly converted into power as an expansion process.
- As in the zenith, the upper sky species are on the head of the human body; then, with the speed, only the force can be converted into power as an expansion process.
- Thus, utilizing loading to power as useful to the human body is achieved
- The condition of equilibrium is achieved at the space element region only. There is no such kind of enemy for space
- Psycho patients also suffer this type of loading; after the load reversal process with speed up in space technology, then useful power is obtained.
- The pressure as a force is divided by the area, then the load is simply the weight as N/m^2 . If putting on sense-level matter of different types, then as lower sky weight, then with the aid of speed in space level as an element, then power is generated, which is required for human beings as in the case of energy creation.

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